

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Clinical Trials in the Pharmaceutical Industry

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Abstract

This research investigates the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in clinical trials, focusing on efficiency, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. To assess current systems and AI's impact, a comprehensive literature review and a structured quantitative survey targeting pharmaceutical professionals were employed. Data were analyzed using statistical tools such as SPSS and Minitab. The primary objective is to understand the efficiency of current systems and how AI can streamline current systems. By understanding both, this research proposes AI as a tool to help significantly reduce the costs and time associated with clinical trials. The research integrates a thorough literature review and a quantitative survey. The survey was distributed to pharmaceutical professionals and included Likert-scale questions and open-ended responses. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics and inferential statistics, including t-tests and regression analysis. The survey results indicate a moderate positive correlation between the perception of AI and the perceived efficiency of clinical trials. A significant positive correlation was found between the perceived potential of AI and the overall efficiency of clinical trials. However, no significant difference was observed in AI perception and its impact between pharma and non-pharma professionals. To conclude, AI has the potential to significantly enhance clinical trial efficiency, particularly in patient recruitment, data management, and trial design. Despite the perceived barriers to adoption, the overall positive perception of AI suggests a promising integration into clinical trials, with benefits for the industry.

Keywords: AI, Clinical Trials, Efficiency, Perceived, Professionals

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1. Introduction

This research investigates the efficiency of current systems within a biotech/pharmaceutical company and the transformative potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in clinical trials within the pharmaceutical industry. It analyses how current systems have performed thus far and highlights how these technologies can streamline drug development within specific business functions, making the process more efficient, accurate, and cost-effective.

1.1. Justification

Clinical trials, crucial for verifying drug safety and efficacy, are traditionally time-consuming, expensive, and prone to high failure rates. With the average drug development costs ranging up to \$1 billion-plus (Schlander et al., 2021) and taking over a decade, innovation is needed. The validation of this dissertation is established through a methodologically sound approach and comprehensive literature review. The research integrates a literature review and structured quantitative survey targeting pharmaceutical professionals to understand the expert insights within the field better. Quantitative analysis employs statistical tools such as SPSS and Minitab to manage and interpret data.

Figure 1

Costs, Time, and Challenges Associated with Clinical Trials

Note. Adapted from *Multistage Clinical Trial Phases with Cost Involved Clinical Trial Phases* (p. 1), by Slide Team, 2022: Slide Team. Copyright 2022 by Slide Team.

The insights from this research fill existing knowledge gaps, such as the lack of studies on perception and impact on pharmaceutical employees themselves. Most of the research surrounding AI in clinical trials to date has been done on a meta-analysis basis, and this research has changed that. It offers practical implications for industry stakeholders and academic researchers, contributing to both academic and practical fields within pharmaceutical research and development. It provides actionable insights and data-driven recommendations that can directly influence industry practices and decision-making processes.

1.2. Justification From a Business Perspective

AI is a growing phenomenon in the business world, and it has made its way into many industries and business functions (Thomas, 2024). Incorporating AI in clinical trials addresses critical challenges such as high costs and lengthy development times. From a business angle, this technology promises significant R&D savings, faster drug development cycles, and competitive market advantages (Mohammed, 2024). They enable more efficient trial designs and quicker, more accurate predictive analyses, potentially reducing time-to-market for new drugs. The justification in this sense is that from a business perspective, time and costs can be saved. Additionally, this research has brought about a new information angle coupled with existing/prior research.

2. Theoretical Framework

This chapter analyses the abundance of prior research regarding AI and its presence in clinical trials. This chapter looks at existing processes and their efficiency, as well as existing theories on how this technology can be used in these processes. The literature review was

conducted across several databases, including Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore, to ensure a complete collection of literature. The search strategy was developed to include a combination of keywords related to "Artificial Intelligence" and "Clinical Trials" within the pharmaceutical industry, as seen in Table 1.

Table 1

Keyword Strings for Literature Review

Keyword Strings
("Artificial Intelligence" OR "AI" OR "Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning") AND ("Quantum Computing" OR "Quantum Simulation" OR "Quantum Algorithms") AND ("Clinical Trials" OR "Biotechnology" OR "Pharmaceuticals" OR "Drug Development") AND "Application" OR "Impact" OR "Innovation" OR "Challenges"
("Artificial Intelligence" OR "AI" OR "Machine Learning" OR "Deep Learning") AND ("Quantum Computing" OR "Quantum Simulation" OR "Quantum Algorithms") AND ("Clinical Trials" OR "Biotechnology" OR "Pharmaceuticals" OR "Drug Development") AND ("Business Functions" OR "Operational Efficiency" OR "Business Strategy" OR "Innovation Management" OR "Product Development" OR "Supply Chain" OR "Marketing" OR "Sales") AND ("Application" OR "Impact" OR "Future Applications" OR "Challenges" OR "Trends")
("artificial intelligence" OR "AI" OR "machine learning" OR "deep learning") AND ("clinical trials" OR "clinical research") AND (applications OR uses OR "use cases" OR implementation OR integration)
"Artificial Intelligence" AND ("clinical trials" OR "clinical research") AND ("pharmaceutical industry" OR "pharma" OR "drug development" OR "drug discovery") AND ("machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "predictive analytics")
"Artificial Intelligence" AND ("patient selection" OR "patient recruitment") AND ("clinical trials" OR "clinical research") AND ("machine learning" OR "deep learning" OR "predictive analytics")

2.1. AI in the Pharmaceutical Industry

AI has made its way into most industries, and its presence has certainly been felt. The pharmaceutical industry is no exception to that phenomenon. As Duran and Chaudhuri (2024) implied, "At present, with its gain in popularity and widespread utilization, almost all

scientific fields are being influenced by the revolution in artificial intelligence.” (p. 1). In this case, scientific fields can be addressed as biotechnology, biology, biochemistry, chemistry, and more. Furthermore, AI has solidified its presence in specific science functions, i.e., drug discovery and development (Duran & Chanduri, 2024). Current applications include trial design, data management, documentation, and endpoint optimization (Licholai, 2023).

Figure 2

An Illustration of Current AI Usage in Clinical Trials

Note. Adapted from *Intelligent clinical trials* (p. 5), by Taylor et al., 2020: Deloitte Insights. Copyright 2020 by Deloitte.

2.2. Drug Discovery and Development

Drug discovery and development is a crucial beginning stage when it comes to clinical trials. However, the challenges of low efficacy, inaccurate deliveries, time, and high costs significantly hinder the progress of drug design and discovery. In simple terms, as described by PharmaCentral (2021), “Drug discovery and development can be described as the sum

total of steps taken by research-intensive entity to identify a new chemical or biological substance and transform it into a product approved for use by patients.” (p. 1). It is the process of searching and identifying chemicals/molecules that may be well-suited for a specific disease.

Figure 3

Demonstration of the Drug Discovery Process

Note. Adapted from *Drug Design and Discovery Special interest group* (p. 1), by FIP - International Pharmaceutical Federation, 2019: International Pharmaceutical Federation. Copyright 2019 by the International Pharmaceutical Federation.

Computer vision (CV) is a key component in drug discovery, which AI can help enhance by combining it with natural language processing (NLP). CV is used in the drug discovery process as a disease biology tool to analyze digital images. Specifically, this technology employs image analysis to compare diseased cells with healthy ones, enhancing the understanding of disease biology. This, in turn, aids in identifying new targets and potential

drug candidates (AI Plus Info, 2022). It has generally been argued that AI is rather successful in CV (Qureshi et al., 2023).

Additionally, virtual screening is a process in the drug discovery phase that AI can help accelerate. According to Niazi (2023), “AI/ML models can screen millions of small molecules, predicting their binding affinity to specific biological targets, a critical factor in drug development” (p. 12). AI can also enhance other processes in drug discovery, such as structure-based design, prediction of toxicity, biomarker identification, drug repurposing, multi-target prediction, and many more (Niazi, 2023).

As demonstrated in Figure 4, AI may help enhance several processes within the drug discovery process.

Figure 4

Visualization of Potential AI/ML Enhancements in Drug Discovery

Note. Adapted from Artificial intelligence for dementia drug discovery and trials

optimization, by Doherty et al., 2023, The Journal of the Alzheimer's Association: Alzheimer's

& Dementia, 19(12), p. 5929 (<https://doi.org/10.1002/alz.13428>). Copyright 2019 by the Journal of the Alzheimer's Association.

A crucial subprocess within drug discovery and design is molecular prediction and design. In this process, thousands of molecules/chemicals are screened and then refined step by step through computational and experimental methods to identify potential candidates with optimal efficacy, safety, and pharmacokinetic properties for further development into therapeutic drugs (Wieder et al., 2020), where they would then transition over to the preclinical and clinical phases in clinical trials.

A significant problem posed during this process is that, like with other processes, it is extremely time-consuming and costly (Wieder et al., 2020). This is where AI comes into the equation, with its use already being felt in molecular discovery (Jain et al., 2023). AI thus far has significantly reduced the drug screening process, resulting in a reduction of costs and, of course, a reduction in time.

For instance, Merck has launched AIDDISON™, an AI-driven platform that integrates drug discovery with synthesis. The platform combines generative AI, machine learning, and computer-aided drug design to screen a vast chemical space of over 60 billion compounds, identifying potential drug candidates with optimal properties such as non-toxicity and stability; this significantly speeds up the drug development process and improves the success rate of new therapies (Baglin, 2023).

2.3. Clinical Trial Design

Clinical trial design is a focal process in the clinical trial process. It occurs directly after the successful completion of the drug discovery process and sets up the molecule for preclinical and clinical testing. The problem here is that the trial design process depends on multiple different factors to ensure its success; while it typically only takes 6 months (Applied Clinical

Trials, 2003), the failure of just one of the different factors, i.e., the trial conduct not matching the trial design, or not engaging patients immediately from the start, can push the company back to the starting point (Pahl, 2020).

With this information, it can be alluded that repetitive failure in trial design would translate into increased costs and a repetitive loss of valuable time. This small problem can affect the entire clinical trial itself and cause it to pause or completely fail. This is where AI may make a positive difference by optimizing the process and subprocesses, leading to a significant cost and time reduction.

AI improves clinical trial design by analyzing electronic health records, patient demographics, previous trial results, and omics data. This allows for the creation of more statistically powerful trials. As a current use or case example, Janssen's partnerships with companies like Komodo Health and Tempus utilize AI to match patients to clinical trials more effectively and identify relevant biomarkers for oncology trials (Komodo Health, 2021).

In a 2024 study on AI's current usage regarding trial design, it was found that AI helped by analyzing historical data, real-world data, and other relevant information to optimize trial protocols, site selection, and patient recruitment. This approach reduced protocol complexity and patient burden, ultimately shortening enrollment times and enhancing trial success rates, both in the long and short terms (Phuong et al., 2024). This evidence further indicates that AI has serious potential to save time and costs.

Figure 5

Demonstration of AI Process Enhancements in Trial Design

Note. Adapted from *Intelligent clinical trials* (p. 6), by Taylor et al., 2020: Deloitte Insights.

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2.4. Data Management and Analysis

Data management is critical across all stages and business processes in clinical trials.

Whether at the beginning during drug discovery, or at the end of a phase three data readout, data management is included in every step. AI algorithms can quickly process and analyze large volumes of data, identifying patterns and insights that humans might miss (Chacko, 2024)

For instance, AI can clean data by detecting and correcting anomalies or duplicates in a fraction of the time it would take human teams, thereby reducing the time required for data review from months to days (Mock et al., 2023).

Moreover, AI supports patient recruitment by analyzing electronic health records (EHRs) to identify potential candidates who meet specific trial criteria, which enhances targeted recruitment efforts and improves enrollment rates. AI also facilitates remote monitoring and real-time data collection, enabling more flexible trial designs and improving patient compliance and data accuracy (Laws, 2024).

Integrating real-world data (RWD) with traditional clinical trial data powered by AI allows for more comprehensive analysis and understanding of treatment effects across diverse patient populations. This approach can lead to the discovery of new therapeutic indications and improve the precision of trial outcomes (Anagnostopoulos et al., 2023).

2.5. Patient Recruitment

AI has become pivotal in enhancing patient recruitment processes, another essential function in clinical trials. Askin et al. (2023) concluded, “Our research indicates that the potential applications of AI across CTs is broad, however recruitment is clearly a key area of interest.” (p. 204). In fact, a 2023 study on the applications of AI in clinical trials found that the area with the highest AI application currently is patient recruiting (Askin et al., 2023). Patient recruiting in clinical trials is essential; if there are no patients for studies, there is no drug development or evidence to support the drug.

Patient recruiting and selection are generally known to be time-consuming, which may affect study outcomes later. In this use case, AI could help speed up the patient selection process, eliminating subpar study outcomes later. Chopra et al. (2023) alluded in their study of AI in clinical trials:

AI can sift through mountains of data to identify subsets of patients who could respond well to a clinical study. Social media material may be analysed to identify hotspots for a disease or disorder, which helps focus the recruitment effort. (p. 4214)

Figure 6

Patient Recruitment Challenges

Note. Adapted from “Clinical trial recruitment infographic”

(<https://www.antidote.me/clinical-trial-recruitment-infographic>). Copyright n.d. by Antidote.

In simple terms, using AI would help read and analyze datasets much quicker than manually doing so. A common problem in patient recruiting is precision when analyzing possible patient data sets. A 2024 study on AI and patient recruitment facilitation in macular degeneration found that AI shortlisted a more significant number of patients (Williamson et al., 2024). In this study, AI demonstrated its superior capabilities compared to ordinary means of search, such as electronic health records (EHRs).

Similarly, in a partnership between Saama Technologies and Pfizer's COVID-19 vaccine trial, AI was used to clean data from over 30,000 patients rapidly, which traditionally would have taken months. This AI application enabled faster data processing and error detection, significantly expediting the trial process (Hutson, 2024). This report is yet another emphasis on the clear potential of AI, especially in the patient selection process within clinical trials.

2.6. Diagnostics

Another critical area in the pharmaceutical industry is diagnostics and diagnosis. AI is now present here, too. Human errors can obstruct accurate diagnoses, and the misreading of information can make tasks challenging and complex. With its diverse applications, AI can ensure higher accuracy and efficiency (Bhattamisra et al., 2023). However, it is important to note that AI is still in the early stages of development when it comes to diagnostics.

To demonstrate this point, as Al-Antari (2023) alluded, "the development and deployment of AI in medical diagnostics are still in the early stages, and there are several technical, regulatory, and ethical challenges that must be overcome for the technology to reach its full potential." (p. 2). What can be concluded from this is that AI is still in the early stages of implementation regarding diagnostics. However, its potential is immense. A 2024 meta-analysis on AI in clinical trials alluded that AI seems to be promising in diagnostics because it can aid in detecting genetic markers and other factors that impact disease progression (Khalifa & Albadawy, 2024).

This is significant, as the traditional ways of genetic testing and assessing/predicting disease progression take a great deal of time and as noted previously, are often subject to failures and discrepancies. For reference, in a MedlinePlus (2021) report, it was noted:

Genetic testing can provide only limited information about an inherited condition. The test often can't determine if a person will show symptoms of a disorder, how severe

the symptoms will be, or whether the disorder will progress over time. Another major limitation is the lack of treatment strategies for many genetic disorders once they are diagnosed. (MedlinePlus, 2021)

This evidence, again, signifies the need for additional AI implementation in diagnostics. With its promising speed in detecting genetic markers and disease progression, AI could not only help diagnose diseases faster but also help diagnostic companies prepare for the progression of specific diseases, such as progressive multiple sclerosis.

The application of AI in diagnostics is multifaceted. For example, in cancer, AI in diagnostics can integrate existing pathology workflows, analyze Whole Slide Images (WSIs) to extract features for diagnostic predictions and identify details that may be challenging for pathologists, enhance sensitivity in detecting isolated tumor cells in lymph nodes, and standardize scoring criteria for tumors (Shafi & Parwani, 2023). Additionally, AI enables content-based image retrieval (CBIR), helping pathologists find similar images in large databases and diagnosing rare and complex cases (Shafi & Parwani, 2023).

Figure 7*Demonstrated Potential of AI in Diagnostics*

Note. Adapted from *HOW IS AI TRANSFORMING MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS?* (p. 1), by Ingenious e-Brain, 2024: Ingenious e-Brain. Copyright 2024 by Ingenious e-Brain.

3. Research Questions

Based on the theoretical framework provided, which highlighted the promising but developing applications of AI in the pharmaceutical industry, this research seeks to dig deeper within a specific domain: clinical trials. The significance of AI in transforming the pharmaceutical industry, as illustrated through real-world applications and expert predictions, sets a strong foundation for exploring their current and potential impact more thoroughly. Consequently, this study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the potential of AI in clinical trials?

2. How do pharmaceutical industry professionals perceive AI's current and future impact on clinical trials?
3. Is there a difference in perception of AI between non-pharma professionals and pharma professionals?

3.1. Hypothesis and Conceptual Models

Considering the need for further evaluation of AI in clinical trials, multiple hypotheses have been formulated to test perception and opinion from industry professionals using a quantitative survey and to assess and further add to existing knowledge of the impact of these technologies using a systematic literature review.

H1: There is a positive correlation between the positive perception of AI and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials

H2: There is a positive correlation between the use of AI in clinical trials and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials

H3: There is a positive correlation between perceived barriers to AI adoption and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials

H4: There is a significant positive correlation between the perceived potential of AI and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials

Figure 8*The Proposed Conceptual Models***4. Methodology**

This study employed a quantitative approach to investigating AI's impact. This research focused on one primary methodology: a quantitative survey targeting pharmaceutical professionals. The quantitative methodology complements the insights from the literature review, providing a comprehensive understanding of the current landscape, perceptions, and future applications of AI in clinical trials.

4.1. Quantitative Survey

A structured questionnaire was developed to gather insights from pharmaceutical professionals regarding their perceptions, awareness, and perceptions of the benefits, challenges, and barriers of implementing AI in clinical trials and future applications for the technology. The survey included Likert-scale questions and open-ended responses to capture a broad range of opinions.

4.1.1. Population and Sampling

The target population comprised professionals within the pharmaceutical industry, including researchers, clinicians, regulatory affairs specialists, and executives. A purposive sampling technique was employed to ensure participants were knowledgeable about or directly involved in clinical trials. The survey was distributed via professional networking sites and industry forums, aiming for an initial sample size of 70 respondents. The questions were structured as closed-ended and utilized a 5-point Likert scale.

The choice of a 5-point Likert scale was based on its clarity for the respondents, offering them a spectrum of response options and the ability to stay neutral on questions they may be uncertain about or prefer not to answer. Additionally, a few open-ended questions were employed merely for opinion analysis but not for statistical analyses and hypotheses testing. The demographics of the survey participants were divided into four categories: age, gender, whether they were pharmaceutical professionals, and if so, what role. For age, participants could select from five age brackets: 18-24, 25-34, 35-44, and 55 plus.

The gender choices were female, male, and diverse. Despite the 70-respondent target, 44 respondents were recorded, and none were excluded due to incomplete data. A complete breakdown of the demographics can be found in Table 2 below.

Table 2*Descriptive Statistics for Survey Participants*

Age Group	Number of Participants
18-24	10
25-34	17
35-44	6
45-54	8
55+	3
Gender	Number of Participants
Female	23
Male	21
Professional Status	Number of Participants
Pharma Professional	24
Non-Pharma Professional	20

4.1.2. Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the survey were analyzed using SPSS and Minitab. Descriptive statistics summarized participant demographics, awareness levels, and perception scores. Inferential statistics, such as t-tests, were applied to examine relationships between pharmaceutical professionals' and non-pharmaceutical professionals' perceptions of AI in clinical trials.

4.1.3. *Sample Reliability and Validity*

In studies involving quantitative methods, it's critical to use a reliable and valid sample. Abbas (2023) alluded, “Validity refers to the extent to which the research measures what it intends to measure, while reliability refers to the consistency and reproducibility of the research results over time” (p. 1). There are multiple methods to assess reliability, but for this study, a Cronbach’s Alpha test was used. To measure validity, the survey was pilot-tested with pharmaceutical professionals to ensure its appropriateness. Table 3 demonstrates the results from the Cronbach’s Alpha test.

Table 3

Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficients

Scale	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Perception of AI	5	.828
Use of AI	4	.729
Perceived Barriers to AI Adoption	4	.665
Perceived Potential of AI	7	.782
Perceived Efficiency of Clinical Trials	5	.822
Overall	25	.942

The data presented in the preceding tables confirm the reliability of all scales. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which can vary between 0 and 1, deems scores above .7 acceptable and those above .8 good (Padilla, 2024). Specifically, the overall scale registered a score of .942, indicating a highly reliable survey sample.

4.1.4. *Limitations*

This study acknowledges limitations related to personal biases, limited demographics, and the survey’s cross-sectional nature, especially considering that these technologies are rapidly evolving. Additionally, a further limitation was the limited total number of participants in the survey. However, efforts were made to mitigate these limitations through multiple pilot tests,

well-structured questions, and a disclaimer introduction notifying respondents to avoid personal biases.

4.1.5. Results and Data Analysis

The survey responses were gathered using a five-point Likert scale and subsequently converted into numeric values for analysis. Table 4 displays the numeric values corresponding to each response.

Table 4

Demonstration of A 5-Point Likert Scale

S. No.	5-Point Likert scale	Numeric
1	Strongly agree	5
2	Agree	4
3	Neutral	3
4	Disagree	2
5	Strongly disagree	1

Note. Adapted from A Technique for the Measurement of Attitudes (pp. 5-55), by R. Likert, 1932: Archives of Psychology.

5. Correlation Analyses and Hypotheses Testing

Spearman correlation analysis is particularly appropriate for quantitative studies using a 5-point Likert scale due to the ordinal nature of the data (Kanda Data, 2023). Likert scales produce ranked data where intervals between ranks are not necessarily equal, making parametric tests like Pearson's correlation unsuitable. Spearman's correlation, a non-parametric measure, does not require data to follow a normal distribution and is adept at handling ordinal data and evaluating the strength and direction of monotonic relationships

between ranked variables, in this case, AI usage, perception, and barriers/challenges coupled with perceived impact.

5.1. Hypotheses Testing Results and Finalized Conceptual Model

Figure 9

Demonstration of Finalized Conceptual Model with Results

Table 5

Correlation and Regression Analyses Results

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
1. Perceived Clinical Trial Efficiency	-	0.43*	0.11**	0.31*	0.64*
2. AI Perception		-			
3. AI Usage			-		
4. Perceived Barriers				-	

5. Perceived Potential						-
------------------------	--	--	--	--	--	---

Note. ** $p < .01$. * $p < .05$.

5.2. AI Perception and Overall Perceived Efficiency of Clinical Trials

H1: There is a positive correlation between the positive perception of AI and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials.

The results of the correlation analysis are demonstrated in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10

Correlation Matrix on AI Perception and Perceived Efficiency

The correlation coefficient between "positive perception of AI" and "higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials" (Impact of AI in this case) was approximately 0.43. This indicates a moderate positive correlation, meaning that as the perception of AI increased, the perceived efficiency of clinical trials increased as well.

Regression Analysis

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the perception of AI (predictor variable) and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials (outcome variable).

Results

The regression model was statistically significant, $F(1, 42) = 9.341$, $p = .004$, with an R^2 of 0.182. This indicates that the perception of AI can explain approximately 18.2% of the variance in the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials.

Table 6 below presents the predictor variable's unstandardized coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values.

Table 6

Summary of Regression AI Perception Versus Perceived Efficiency

Variable	B	SE(B)	β	t	p
Constant	2.65	0.39		6.73	<.001
Perception of AI	0.34	0.11	0.43	3.06	.004

The regression equation is $\text{Impact of AI} = 2.65 + 0.34 \times \text{Perception of AI}$

This positive coefficient ($B = 0.34$, $p = .004$) indicates that a higher perception of AI scores is associated with a higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trial scores. This, coupled with the correlation coefficient of 0.43, has led to the acceptance of H1.

5.3. AI Usage and Overall Perceived Efficiency of Clinical Trials

H2: There is a positive correlation between the use of AI in clinical trials and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials.

Figure 11

Correlation Matrix on AI Usage and Perceived Efficiency

The correlation coefficient between "AI usage" and "higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials" was 0.11, indicating a very weak correlation.

Regression Analysis

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between AI usage and higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials. The predictor variable was AI usage, and the outcome variable was higher perceived efficiency.

Results

The regression model was not statistically significant: $F(1,42) = 0.543$, $p = .465$, with an R^2 of .013. This indicated that only 1.3% of the variance in higher perceived efficiency can be explained by AI usage.

Table 7 presents the unstandardized coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for the predictor variable.

Table 7

Summary of Regression AI Usage Versus Perceived Efficiency

Variable	B	SE(B)	β	t	p
Constant	3.59	0.35		10.24	<.001
AI Usage	0.07	0.10	0.11	0.74	.465

The regression equation was: Higher Perceived Overall Efficiency of Clinical Trials = 3.59 + 0.07 \times AI Usage

This weak positive coefficient (B=0.07, p =.465p) indicated that higher AI usage scores are associated with slightly higher perceived efficiency scores, but this relationship is not statistically significant. This has led to the rejection of H2.

5.4. Barriers to AI Adoption and Overall Perceived Efficiency of Clinical Trials

H3: There is a positive correlation between perceived barriers to AI adoption and the perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials

Figure 12

Correlation Matrix on Perceived Barriers and Perceived Efficiency

The correlation coefficient between "perceived barriers to AI adoption" and "higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials" was 0.31, indicating a weak positive correlation.

Regression Analysis

A linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between "perceived barriers to AI adoption" and "higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials". The predictor variable was "perceived barriers to AI adoption," and the outcome variable was "higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials".

Results

The regression model was statistically significant: $F(1,42) = 4.430$, $p = .004$, with an R^2 of .095. This indicates that approximately 9.5% of the variance in "higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials" can be explained by the "perceived barriers to AI adoption."

Table 8 presents the unstandardized coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for the predictor variable.

Table 8

Summary of Regression Barriers Versus Perceived Efficiency

Variable	B	SE(B)	β	t	p
Constant	2.77	0.51		5.38	<.001
Perceived Barriers to AI Adoption	0.28	0.14	0.31	2.11	.004

The regression equation was: Higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials = 2.77 + 0.28 × perceived barriers to adoption

This positive coefficient (B = 0.28, p = .004) indicated that higher perceived barriers to AI adoption scores are associated with higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trial scores. This, in conjunction with the positive correlation coefficient (0.31), has led to the acceptance of H3.

5.5. Perceived Potential of AI and Overall Perceived Efficiency of Clinical Trials

H4: There is a significant positive correlation between the perceived potential of AI and the perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials

Figure 13

Correlation Matrix on Future Potential and Higher Perceived Efficiency

The correlation coefficient between "perceived potential of AI " and "higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials" was 0.64. This indicates an average positive correlation, insinuating that as the perceived potential of AI adoption increases, the perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials significantly increases.

Regression Analysis

A subsequent regression analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between the perceived potential of AI and the overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials.

Results

The regression model was statistically significant, $F(1,42) = 29.26$, $p < .001$, with an R^2 of 0.411, indicating that approximately 41.1% of the variance in higher perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials can be explained by the perceived potential of AI.

Table 9 presents the unstandardized coefficients, standard errors, t-values, and p-values for the predictor variable.

Table 9

Summary of Regression Perceived Potential of AI and Perceived Efficiency

Variable	B	SE(B)	β	t	p
Constant	2.00	0.35		5.81	<.001
Perceived (Future) Potential of AI	0.49	0.09	0.64	5.41	<.001

The regression equation was: Higher perceived efficiency = 2.00 + 0.49 ×
future potential of AI

This positive coefficient (B = 0.49, p = <.001) indicated that higher scores on the perceived potential of AI are associated with higher scores on the perceived overall efficiency of clinical trials. This, in addition to the previously demonstrated positive correlation coefficient (0.64), has led to the acceptance of H4.

5.6. Research Question Results

In addition to hypothesis testing, a multitude of statistical analyses were employed to further evaluate the research questions.

5.6.1. Perception and Impact of AI Between Pharma Professionals and Non-Professionals

This research had a plethora of questions as well as motives. However, one specific question that was to be analyzed was whether there was a difference in the perception of AI between pharmaceutical professionals and non-professionals. An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare AI perception scores between pharma professionals and non-pharma professionals.

The t-test results indicated that there was no significant difference in AI perception scores between pharma professionals ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 0.52$) and non-pharma professionals ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.81$); $t(42) = 0.964$, $p = 0.341$. The t-value of 0.964 suggested that the difference between the groups' scores is small relative to the variability within the groups (Maio et al., 2024). Since the p-value of 0.341 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, there is no statistically significant difference in AI perception scores between the two groups.

Tables 10 and 11 demonstrate the mean and standard deviation, t-scores, and p-values, respectively.

Table 10

Descriptive Statistics for AI Perception Scores

Group	N	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Pharma Professionals	24	3.64	0.52
Non-Pharma Professionals	20	3.44	0.81

Table 11

Independent Samples T-test for AI Perception Scores

t	df	p-value
0.964	42	0.341

Similarly, an independent samples t-test was conducted to compare AI's current impact on clinical trial scores between pharma professionals and non-pharma professionals.

Results

The results of the t-test indicated that there was no significant difference in perceptions of AI's current impact on clinical trials between pharma professionals ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.67$, $N = 24$) and non-pharma professionals ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.59$, $N = 20$), $t(42) = -0.89$, $p = .380$.

Table 12*Group Statistics for Current Impact of AI in Clinical Trials*

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pharma Professionals	24	3.78	0.67
Non-Pharma Professionals	20	3.95	0.59

Table 13*Independent Samples T-test for AI Impact Scores*

t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
-0.89	42	.380	-0.17	0.19

These results suggest that the professional background (pharma vs. non-pharma) does not significantly affect perceptions of AI's impact on clinical trials. Both groups had relatively similar opinions regarding AI's current impact on clinical trials.

5.6.1.1. Results and Discussion

An independent samples t-test was conducted to compare AI perception scores between pharmaceutical professionals and non-professionals. The results showed no significant difference between the two groups: pharma professionals (M = 3.64, SD = 0.52) and non-pharma professionals (M = 3.44, SD = 0.81); $t(42) = 0.964$, $p = 0.341$.

Similarly, another t-test comparing perceptions of AI's impact on clinical trials found no significant difference: pharma professionals (M = 3.78, SD = 0.67) and non-pharma professionals (M = 3.95, SD = 0.59); $t(42) = -0.89$, $p = 0.380$.

These results signify that professional background does not significantly affect perceptions of AI or its current impact on clinical trials. Both groups shared similar views, suggesting a common attitude towards AI regardless of professional field.

5.6.2. *Pharma Industry Professionals' Perception of AI's Current and Future Impact*

Descriptive statistics were calculated for various aspects of clinical trials to examine the perception of AI impact among pharma professionals. The following percentages of pharma professionals indicated that AI had a positive impact (i.e., a rating of 4 or 5) on different aspects:

- **Trial Site Selection:** 75% of pharma professionals found that AI had a positive impact.
- **Patient Selection/Recruiting:** 62.5% of pharma professionals found that AI had a positive impact.
- **Resource Optimization:** 91.7% of pharma professionals found that AI had a positive impact.
- **Trial Design/Methodology:** 62.5% of pharma professionals found that AI had a positive impact.
- **Data Management/Analysis:** 75% of pharma professionals found that AI had a positive impact.

Table 14

Descriptive Statistics on AI Impact for Pharma Professionals

Measure	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
AI Impact on Trial Site Selection	3.42	0.67
AI Impact on Patient Selection	3.42	0.72
AI Impact on Resource Optimization	3.88	0.58
AI Impact on Trial Design	3.42	0.67
AI Impact on Data Mgmt./Analysis	3.75	0.62

Future Impact

Descriptive statistics were calculated to assess pharma professionals' perceptions regarding AI's future in clinical trials. The following percentages of pharma professionals indicated agreement (i.e., a rating of 4 or 5) with the statements about the future impact of AI:

- **AI will become a standard tool in clinical trials within the next decade:** 83.3% of pharma professionals agreed.
- **AI in the future will lead to a significant reduction in the costs associated with clinical trials:** 70.8% of pharma professionals agreed.
- **AI will accelerate the drug development process through more efficient clinical trials:** 66.7% of pharma professionals agreed.

Table 15

Descriptive Statistics for Pharma Professionals' Future Perceptions

Measure	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)
AI will become a standard tool in clinical trials within the next decade	3.75	0.75
AI in the future will lead to a significant reduction in the costs associated with clinical trials	3.83	0.72
AI will accelerate the drug development process through more efficient clinical trials	3.58	0.83

5.6.3. The Potential of AI in Clinical Trials

For this research question, a series of descriptive statistical analyses were employed to further assess AI's potential.

Table 16*Word Frequency of AI Potential in Clinical Trials*

Word	Frequency
Faster trials	10
data	8
efficiency	5
none	5
time	3
knowledge	2
improvements	2
better	2
options	2
like	2
ai	2
analysis	2
human	2
trials	2
improve	2
speed	2
makes	2
processes	2
course	1
a lot	1

Thematic Analysis

Based on the theme frequencies from open-ended questions regarding AI's potential, responses can be broadly categorized into the following themes:

1. Efficiency and Speed:
 1. Faster assessment of results
 2. Timesaving
2. Data Management:
 1. Improved data collection
 2. Better data analysis
3. Overall Improvement:
 1. Enhanced efficiency

2. Better treatment options
4. Human Factors:
 1. Improved human processes
 2. Reduction of human errors
5. AI Capabilities:
 1. AI's role in analysis
 2. AI in improving processes

Table 17*Thematic Analysis of AI Potential in Clinical Trials*

Theme	Count
Efficiency and Speed	17
Data Management Improvements	7
Overall Improvement	6
Human Factors	4
AI Capabilities	3

Discussion

This analysis highlights that the most perceived potential of AI in clinical trials is related to increasing the efficiency and speed of clinical trials. Data management and overall improvements are also prominent, indicating that AI is expected to enhance various aspects of clinical trial processes. Human factors and specific AI capabilities are mentioned less frequently but still recognized as significant.

Further Descriptive Analyses

This report provides a detailed statistical analysis to gather insights into respondents' perceptions of AI's current impact on different aspects of clinical trials. The respondents'

roles were mapped to their responses, and both descriptive and comparative statistical analyses were performed.

The following table provides the mean, median, and standard deviation of responses for each question grouped by the role of the pharmaceutical professionals.

Table 18

Demonstration of Mean, Median, and SD of Respondents

Role	Site Selection	Site Selection	Site Selection	Patient Recruitment	Patient Recruitment	Patient Recruitment	Optimizes Resources	Optimizes Resources	Optimizes Resources	Improves Data Management	Improves Data Management	Improves Data Management	Improves Trial Design	Improves Trial Design	Improves Trial Design
	mean	median	std	mean	median	std	mean	median	std	mean	median	std	mean	median	std
Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls	3.50	3.50	0.71	3.50	3.50	0.71	3.50	3.50	2.12	3.50	3.50	0.71	3.50	3.50	0.71
Clinical Trial Associate/Lead/Manager	3.25	3.00	0.50	3.25	3.00	0.50	3.50	3.50	0.58	3.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	3.00	0.82
Other (please specify)	3.91	4.00	0.68	3.79	4.00	0.78	4.24	4.00	0.50	4.03	4.00	0.81	3.76	4.00	0.90
Preclinical/Research Scientist	3.33	3.00	0.58	3.33	3.00	0.58	4.00	4.00	0.00	3.67	4.00	0.58	3.67	4.00	0.58
Regulatory Affairs	3.50	3.50	0.71	3.50	3.50	2.12	4.00	4.00	1.41	4.50	4.50	0.71	4.50	4.50	0.71

Next Steps: Comparative Analysis

ANOVA was employed to determine if there were statistically significant differences in responses among different roles for each question.

ANOVA Results

The ANOVA tests were conducted to determine if there were statistically significant differences in responses among different roles for each question. The results are presented in the following table.

Table 19

ANOVA Test Demonstrating Statistical Differences in Opinion

Question	F-value	p-value
AI improves site selection	1.4692	0.2302
AI improves recruitment	0.6067	0.6602
AI optimizes resources	1.7991	0.1486
AI improves data management	2.1536	0.0924
AI improves design	1.1256	0.3585

Interpretation of ANOVA Results

The ANOVA results indicate the following:

- None of the p-values are below the common significance level of 0.05. This suggests that there are no statistically significant differences in the responses to the questions among the different roles of pharma professionals.

Given these results, performing post-hoc tests are unnecessary because the ANOVA did not reveal significant differences (Bobbit, 2019).

Summary

1. **Descriptive Statistics:** This research calculated the mean, median, and standard deviation of responses for each question grouped by role.

2. **Comparative Analysis:** ANOVA tests showed no significant differences in responses among different roles for any of the questions.

Observations

While the ANOVA results did not show statistically significant differences, the descriptive statistics reveal some notable trends in the perceptions of different roles:

1. The 'Other (please specify)' role generally shows higher mean responses for most questions, indicating a more positive perception of AI's benefits.
2. 'Clinical Trial Associate/Lead/Manager' tends to have lower mean responses across questions, suggesting a more reserved view of AI's impact.
3. 'Regulatory Affairs' sees significant benefits of AI in data management and trial design.

Visualizations

The following bar plots visualize the mean responses for each question grouped by the roles of pharma professionals. They help illustrate the differences in perceptions among various roles.

Figure 14

Bar Plot Demonstrating Patient Recruitment Answers

Figure 15

Bar Plot Demonstrating Trial Site Selection Answers

Figure 16

Bar Plot Demonstrating Data Mgmt. and Analysis Answers

Figure 17

Bar Plot Demonstrating Resource Optimization Answers

Figure 18

Bar Plot Demonstrating Trial Design Answers

Results

The bar plots illustrated the mean responses for each question grouped by the roles of pharmaceutical professionals. Several notable trends emerge from these visualizations:

1. **AI Improves Site Selection:** The role categorized as "Other (please specify)," i.e., IR/PR, Chief Medical/Executive/Operational/Scientific Officer, General Counsel consistently showed the highest mean response, indicating a strong belief in AI's ability to enhance the selection of trial sites. In contrast, "Clinical Trial Associate/Lead/Manager" roles tend to have lower mean responses, suggesting a more cautious view on this benefit of AI.

2. **AI Improves Recruitment:** Like site selection, the "Other (please specify)" group also perceives AI to significantly improve patient recruitment and selection. The responses from other roles, such as "Regulatory Affairs" and "Preclinical/Research Scientist," are relatively uniform, indicating moderate agreement with this statement.
3. **AI Optimizes Resources:** The "Other (please specify)" role again stands out with higher mean responses, indicating a strong belief in AI's ability to optimize resource use in clinical trials. Other roles show a more conservative but positive outlook, with mean responses clustered closely together.
4. **AI Improves Data Management:** "Regulatory Affairs" professionals exhibit the highest mean response for this question, highlighting a belief in AI's potential to enhance data management and analysis. In contrast, "Clinical Trial Associate/Lead/Manager" roles display lower mean responses, suggesting varying levels of confidence in AI's capabilities across different roles.
5. **AI Improves Trial Design:** The perception that AI can improve the overall design and methodology of trials is most strongly held by "Regulatory Affairs" professionals, as indicated by their high mean responses. Meanwhile, other roles, such as "Preclinical/Research Scientist" and "Clinical Trial Associate/Lead/Manager," show lower but still positive mean responses.

These visual trends, though not statistically significant according to the ANOVA results, demonstrated how different professional roles perceive the benefits of AI in clinical trials. They suggested that while there is a consensus on the positive impact of AI, the degree of confidence varies among roles, with some groups exhibiting stronger beliefs in AI's potential than others.

6. Results Discussion

The analysis revealed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.43$) between the positive perception of AI and the higher overall perceived efficiency of clinical trials. This suggests that pharmaceutical professionals who have a favorable view of AI also perceive clinical trials using AI as more efficient. The regression analysis supported this finding, with the perception of AI explaining 18.2% of the variance in perceived efficiency ($R^2 = 0.182$, $p = 0.004$). This implies that fostering a positive perception of AI could significantly enhance the perceived efficiency of clinical trials. The industry should consider strategies to improve AI perception among professionals, such as through education and training, successful case studies, and demonstrating tangible benefits.

Contrary to expectations, the correlation between AI usage and the perceived efficiency of clinical trials was very weak ($r = 0.11$). The regression model was also not statistically significant ($R^2 = 0.013$, $p = 0.465$), indicating that AI usage does not substantially influence the perceived efficiency of clinical trials. This outcome suggests that simply implementing or using AI is not enough to alter perceptions of efficiency. It highlights the importance of effective integration and utilization of AI technologies rather than mere adoption. This further solidifies the point that the industry should focus on best practices for AI implementation through education to ensure that professionals realize its potential benefits.

The findings showed a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.31$) between perceived barriers to AI adoption and higher perceived efficiency of clinical trials. The regression analysis indicated that perceived barriers could explain 9.5% of the variance in efficiency perceptions ($R^2 = 0.095$, $p = 0.004$). This counterintuitive result suggests that recognizing and addressing barriers to AI adoption might be associated with better preparation and, consequently, higher efficiency in clinical trials. Notable barriers found in this study were data privacy and

security, lack of trust in AI, difficulty in integration with existing systems, and regulatory hurdles.

The correlation between the perceived potential of AI and the perceived efficiency of clinical trials was moderate to strong ($r = 0.64$). The regression analysis further demonstrated that perceived potential could explain 41.1% of the variance in efficiency perceptions ($R^2 = 0.411$, $p < 0.001$). This strong relationship suggests that belief in AI's future capabilities significantly boosts the perceived efficiency of clinical trials. This finding once again emphasizes the importance of communicating AI's potential through training programs, successful use case examples, and more.

The t-test results indicated no significant difference in AI perception and impact scores between pharmaceutical professionals and non-professionals. This suggests a uniform attitude towards AI's impact on clinical trials across different professional backgrounds, highlighting a consensus on AI's potential benefits and challenges.

Descriptive statistics showed that a significant proportion of pharma professionals believe that AI currently positively impacts various aspects of clinical trials, including trial site selection (75%), patient recruitment (62.5%), resource optimization (91.7%), trial design (62.5%), and data management (75%). For future impact, a high percentage of professionals agreed that AI would become a standard tool in clinical trials (83.3%), lead to significant cost reductions (70.8%), and accelerate drug development (66.7%). These perceptions indicate strong support for AI's integration and potential to transform clinical trials, suggesting that ongoing investments in AI technologies and training are likely to be well-received and beneficial.

The thematic analysis highlighted that respondents perceive AI's most significant potential in increasing the efficiency and speed of clinical trials, improving data management, and overall

enhancing trial processes. Human factors and specific AI capabilities were also recognized, albeit less frequently.

6.1. Results in Comparison to Previous Literature

The findings of this study align closely with several key points highlighted in the literature review. For instance, Phuong et al. (2024) found that AI significantly helped speed up and optimize trial design, site selection, and patient recruitment. This was mirrored in this study, where a substantial proportion of pharmaceutical professionals indicated that AI had a positive current impact on these same areas: 75% for trial site selection, 62.5% for patient recruitment, and 62.5% for trial design.

Moreover, Licholai (2023) identified data management and trial design as prominent current applications of AI in clinical trials. This study's findings are consistent with those observations. A significant portion of pharmaceutical professionals surveyed indicated that AI had a positive impact on data management (75%) and trial design (62.5%). These results align with Licholai's (2023) findings, reinforcing the role of AI in these critical areas.

Laws (2024) reported that AI enabled more flexible trial designs, which is echoed in this study's findings. As noted by 75% of the respondents, AI's role in enhancing data management and analysis contributes to the flexibility and adaptability of trial designs. The ability to process and analyze large volumes of data in real time allows for more dynamic and responsive trial protocols, which can be adjusted based on ongoing results and emerging data trends.

Askin et al. (2023) found that AI's most prominent current application in clinical trials is in patient recruiting. This study's findings corroborate that assertion, as 62.5% of pharmaceutical professionals surveyed indicated that AI had a positive impact on patient selection and recruitment. This acknowledgment of AI's role in patient recruitment aligns

well with Askin et al. (2023), solidifying AI's presence in patient recruitment. Similarly, these findings correlate with those of Williamson et al. (2024) and Hutson (2024).

Jain et al. (2023) found that AI has significantly reduced the drug screening process, resulting in lower costs and reduced time in molecular discovery and design. This study's findings align with Jain et al.'s observations, as 64% of respondents indicated that AI positively impacts the drug discovery process.

Furthermore, the findings related to perceived barriers to AI adoption and their counterintuitive positive correlation with perceived efficiency suggest a nuanced understanding within the industry. Recognizing barriers might lead to better preparation and more strategic implementation, as suggested by the positive association found in this study. This insight complements the literature's emphasis on the need to address technical, regulatory, and ethical challenges to fully leverage AI's potential in clinical trials (Al-Antari, 2023; Bhattamisra et al., 2023).

The strong correlation ($r = 0.64$) between the perceived potential of AI and the perceived efficiency of clinical trials found in this study also aligns with the optimistic outlook presented in the literature. Studies have consistently projected that AI will become an integral tool in clinical trials, significantly reducing costs and accelerating drug development (Mohammed, 2024; Duran & Chaudhuri, 2024). This alignment demonstrates a consensus in both academic research and industry perceptions regarding the potential of AI in clinical trials.

7. Conclusion

The integration of AI in clinical trials presents a transformative potential for the pharmaceutical industry, significantly impacting efficiency, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. This research has demonstrated that AI can enhance various aspects of clinical trials, including patient recruitment, data management, and trial design. The positive perception of AI among pharmaceutical professionals correlates with higher perceived efficiency of clinical trials, suggesting that fostering a favorable view of AI through education and training can further enhance its adoption and effectiveness.

Despite AI's promising potential, the study also highlighted some challenges. The weak correlation between AI usage and perceived efficiency indicates that mere implementation is not sufficient. Effective integration and utilization of AI technologies are crucial to realizing their full benefits. Additionally, perceived barriers such as data privacy, lack of trust, integration difficulties, and regulatory hurdles must be addressed to optimize AI adoption.

Future research should focus on developing best practices for AI implementation in clinical trials, emphasizing the importance of strategic integration and utilization. Exploring ways to mitigate the identified barriers can also enhance AI's effectiveness and acceptance within the industry. Moreover, longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into the long-term impacts of AI on clinical trials, helping to refine and optimize its application further.

Overall, the positive outlook on AI's potential, supported by significant correlations between its perceived future capabilities and trial efficiency, underscores the need for ongoing investments in AI technologies and training. Such efforts are likely to be well-received and beneficial, ultimately accelerating drug development processes and reducing associated costs.

This research contributed valuable insights to both academic and practical fields within pharmaceutical research and development, offering actionable recommendations that can directly influence industry practices and decision-making processes. Continued exploration and strategic implementation of AI hold the promise of significantly transforming clinical trials, paving the way for more efficient and effective drug development in the future.

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